

**Impact of extracorporeal cardiopulmonary
resuscitation on neurological prognosis and survival
in adult patients after cardiac arrest: an individual
pooled matched patient data meta-analysis**

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Introduction

Sudden cardiac arrest (CA) is a leading cause of cardiovascular death worldwide, with approximately 500,000 cases per year in North America (1). Despite significant advancements in recent decades, survival rates for both in-hospital cardiac arrest (IHCA) and out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) remain disappointingly low (2). Several therapeutic strategies have been introduced, including target temperature management (TTM) following return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC) and immediate coronary angiogram with percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) after ROSC. However, the effectiveness of these interventions in improving patient outcomes remains controversial and the identification of suitable patient populations for these treatments is still uncertain (3-5).

Conventional cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CCPR) focuses on initiating early resuscitation maneuvers, particularly chest compressions, to reduce "no-flow time" and enhance the chances of successful recovery and survival (6). However, even with proper execution of CCPR, achieving ROSC is not guaranteed for a significant number of patients (7). Furthermore, among those who do achieve ROSC, prolonged resuscitation attempts significantly decrease the probability of favorable long-term neurological outcomes (8,9).

In cases of refractory CA unresponsive to CCPR, the initiation of veno-arterial extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO), i.e. extracorporeal cardiopulmonary resuscitation (ECPR), during resuscitation has shown promise. ECPR extends the available time for resuscitation, preserves organ function, reduces the need for inotropic and vasopressor drugs, lowers myocardial oxygen consumption and potentially facilitates cardiac recovery (10). Additionally, when combined with a heat exchanger, ECPR enables rapid induction and stable maintenance of hypothermia, which may have neuroprotective effects in this context (11). ECPR also allows for investigation and treatment of potential underlying causes, such as coronary occlusion or pulmonary thromboembolism (12).

Despite its potential benefits, ECPR is an invasive and potentially traumatic intervention, associated with various complications, including hemolysis, coagulopathy and bleeding, acute kidney injury, limb ischemia, and severe pulmonary edema (13). Successful vascular cannulation for ECPR requires technical expertise and surgical skills. Consequently, three randomized trials have shown different effects of ECPR in OHCA patient (14-16). Observational studies have reported more conflicting results (17,18) and limitations in study design have hindered comprehensive meta-analysis of available data (19).

An individual participant data (IPD) meta-analysis offers advantages over aggregate meta-analysis, allowing for the inclusion of individual patient characteristics in the analyses.

The aim of this study was therefore to evaluate the impact of ECPR on neurological outcomes and mortality compared to CCPR, with a specific focus on predefined subgroups, using a matched IPD meta-analysis.

Methods

Protocol and registration

The IPD meta-analysis was performed following the methodologies recommended by the IPD Meta-analysis Methods Group of the Cochrane Collaboration (at <https://methods.cochrane.org/ipdma/about-ipd-meta-analyses>). The study protocol was registered with the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO) and last updated on November 30, 2020 (CRD42020160685). This meta-analysis was not pre-planned.

Data sources and Search strategies

A systematic literature search was performed up to the 13th of December 2020 in the PubMed, EMBASE and CENTRAL databases using the following Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms: "heart arrest" AND/OR "extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation" AND/OR "resuscitation" AND/OR "neurological disease" AND/OR "mortality". Only studies including an ECPR and a control (i.e. CCPR) group that reported either neurological outcome and/or mortality were eligible. As data collection was slowed down because of the COVID-19 pandemic, the search was updated twice, on the 31th December 2021 and on the 20th of October 2022. Moreover, the authors of a recently published randomized clinical trial (20) were also contacted to include their data in the final analysis.

The search included only original studies published in English in peer-reviewed journals. The complete research string for each database as well as the main research questions, with reference to participants, interventions, comparisons, outcomes and study design (PICOS), are reported in **Supplemental Table S1**. In addition, we searched the reference lists of eligible studies and relevant reviews for additional published data, searched by contacting experts, and used a web search for abstracts, proceedings, and unpublished studies. Finally, one recently published systematic review was also considered to assess for completeness of data research (20). Details about study screening and selection, as well data extraction are reported in **Supplemental Material**.

Data collection

For the purpose of this study, we collected demographic data, the presence of several comorbidities, the year of admission, the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) length of stay, CA characteristics (i.e. location of arrest, witnessed arrest, bystander CPR, cause of arrest, initial rhythm). Whenever available, the time to the end of resuscitation (i.e. return of spontaneous

circulation or ECPR implementation or termination of CPR) and the lactate levels on admission were also collected. The use of coronary angiography or targeted temperature management (TTM, i.e. $<36^{\circ}\text{C}$ of body temperature with active therapy) was noted. Patients were considered until the last day of follow-up according to the study design; mortality and time to death were collected as well as the occurrence of unfavorable functional outcome, defined as a Cerebral Performance Category (CPC) scale of 3-5. We also collected whether the patient was considered for organ donation and whether organ donation eventually occurred. All available data were retrieved from the original databases and no additional research for missing information was requested. The list of requested variable is reported in the **Supplemental Material**.

Study Outcomes

The primary outcome of the IPD meta-analysis was to assess the impact of ECPR on the occurrence of unfavorable functional outcome, whenever it was assessed, in comparison with CCPR. Secondary outcomes were: a) the impact of ECPR on mortality (whenever it has collected); b) time to event (i.e. mortality, censored at 90 days after CA). Functional outcome and mortality were also analyzed in predefined subgroups, including initial rhythm (i.e. shockable vs non-shockable), location of arrest (IHCA vs. OHCA) and origin of arrest (cardiac vs. non-cardiac). Exploratory analyses, due to a relevant number of missing values, included the effects of time to the end of resuscitation and lactate levels on functional outcome and mortality.

Statistical analysis

All variables were harmonized into a single file, which was checked for consistency. In RCTs and in studies reporting matched-control populations, original data were included in the IPD. In non-randomized studies with unmatched populations, a propensity score including age, location of arrest and initial rhythm was performed by an independent statistician and used to match ECPR and CCPR patients in a 1:1 ratio for each study; time to resuscitation, which was initially considered as one variable for the matching process, was eventually removed because of several missing values. The propensity score was derived from a logistic regression model included the selected variables; each patient was assigned a propensity score reflecting the probability of receiving ECPR. All selected variables showed a standardized mean difference (SMD) < 0.10 , reflecting a good matching. Study outcomes analyses were performed only for “matched” patients, to correct for baseline imbalances of non-randomized trials.

Categorical variables will be presented as numbers (%); continuous variables will be presented as means (\pm standard deviation) or medians (interquartile range [IQR]), as appropriate. We will compare the characteristics and outcomes of ECPR patients with CCPR patients using Mann-Whitney U test, t-test, Chi-2 test, or Fisher exact test, as appropriate. Unfavorable outcome and mortality will be analyzed using multilevel mixed-effects generalized linear models using a logit-link function and binomial family with “site” as a random intercept using an exchangeable covariance matrix. Odds ratios and their 95% Confidence Intervals (CI) will be computed.

Survival are censored at 90 days for all patients with available long-term follow-up or at the last available day, as reported in the database; Kaplan-Meier analysis plot will be used to assess the proportion of survivors between the two groups. To assess the independent association between lactate levels on admission or time to the end of resuscitation with study outcomes, we will treat these two variables as a linear, continuous value in which the former was categorized as intervals of 5 mEq/L and the last as intervals of 10 minutes. Both lactate and time to ROSC with their interactions with ECPR/CCPR groups will be considered in the modelling. All the analyses are performed using Stata/SE 17.0 for Windows and R software, version 4.0.3 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing). Statistical significance are set at 2-tailed P value < 0.05 .

Results

Presentation of results will be as follow:

Study selection

Study population

Study Outcomes

Subgroup Analyses

Exploratory analyses (i.e. lactate levels and time to termination of resuscitation)

Table 1: Demographic data of the study population, according to the use of conventional (CCPR) or extracorporeal (ECPR) cardiopulmonary resuscitation. Data are presented as count (%) or median (IQR).

	All Patients (n=)	CCPR (n=)	ECPR (n=)	<i>P value</i>
Age, years				
Male Gender, n (%)				
Included in matched or randomized studies, n (%)				
Witnessed CA, n (%)				
Bystander CPR, n (%)				
Time to ROSC/ECMO, min *				
Out of Hospital CA				
Cardiac Origin CA				
Shockable Rhythm, n (%)				
Chronic Heart Failure, n (%)				
Hypertension, n (%)				
Coronary Artery Disease, n (%)				
Diabetes, n (%)				
COPD/Asthma, n (%)				
Neurological Disease, n (%)				
Chronic Renal Disease, n (%)				
Liver Cirrhosis, n (%)				
First available Lactate, mEq/L**				
Hypothermia, n (%)				
Coronary Angiography, n (%)				

ICU stay, days				
Mortality, n (%)				
Unfavorable Neurological Outcome, n (%)				
Organ Donation Candidate, n (%)				
Organ Donor, n (%)				

ICU = intensive care unit; CA = cardiac arrest; CPR = cardiopulmonary resuscitation; ROSC = return of spontaneous circulation; VF/VT = ventricular fibrillation/ventricular tachycardia; COPD = chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; ECPR = extracorporeal cardiopulmonary resuscitation; CRRT = continuous renal replacement therapy; MV = mechanical ventilation; TTM = targeted temperature management

Table 2: Study outcomes in subgroup analyses, according to the use of conventional (CCPR) or extracorporeal (ECPR) cardiopulmonary resuscitation. Data are presented as count (%). OR = odds ratio; CI = confidence intervals; UO = unfavorable functional outcome; OHCA = out-of-hospital cardiac arrest; IHCA = in-hospital cardiac arrest.

		CCPR (n=)	ECPR (n=)	OR (95% CI)	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interaction</i>
Mortality	<i>Shockable Rhythm</i>					
	<i>Non-Shockable Rhythm</i>					
UO	<i>Shockable Rhythm</i>					
	<i>Non-Shockable Rhythm</i>					
Mortality	<i>OHCA</i>					
	<i>IHCA</i>					
UO	<i>OHCA</i>					
	<i>IHCA</i>					
Mortality	<i>Cardiac Origin</i>					
	<i>Non-Cardiac Origin</i>					
UO	<i>Cardiac Origin</i>					
	<i>Non-Cardiac Origin</i>					

Figures

Figure 1. Study outcomes in the extracorporeal (ECPR) and conventional cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CCPR) groups. UO = unfavorable functional outcome; OHCA = out-of-hospital cardiac arrest; IHCA = in-hospital cardiac arrest.

Figure 2: Kaplan-Meier plot of the survival curves in the matched extracorporeal cardiopulmonary resuscitation (ECPR) group and the matched conventional cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CCPR) group, censored at 90 days after arrest.

Figure 3: Adjusted prediction of unfavorable neurological outcome (mean and 95% CIs) according to the time to termination of resuscitation (minutes) or lactate levels on admission.

Figure 4: Adjusted prediction of death according to the time to termination of resuscitation (minutes) or lactate levels on admission.

Figure 5: Adjusted prediction of unfavorable neurological outcome or death according to the combination of time to termination of resuscitation (minutes) and lactate levels on admission.

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Supplemental Material

Methods

Study screening and selection

Two authors (GC and AM) independently screened study titles and abstracts for potential eligibility and assessed their validity. Disagreement between authors was assessed and resolved through a third reviewer (FST), who reviewed the original text of the article.

We enrolled only studies evaluating ECPR in adults (i.e., >18 years of age) CA patients in either randomized clinical trials (RCT, including individual and cluster-randomized trials) or observational studies, either retrospective or prospective. Editorials, commentaries, letters to editor, opinion articles, reviews, meeting abstracts, case reports and studies published in other languages were also excluded, as well as original articles lacking abstract and/or quantitative details on neurological outcome and survival and studies conducted on animal models. When multiple publications of the same research group/center described case series with potential overlap, the more recent publication, if eligible, was considered.

Data Extraction

Two authors (AM and FA) extracted general information from each manuscript using a pre-defined standardized data extraction form, including minimal descriptive data for each study. Any discrepancies were identified and resolved via discussion. Corresponding authors of all identified studies were contacted to provide raw individual level data. In case of no response, the authors were recontacted twice. In case of no further response, other co-authors were also contacted. The data were reviewed for completeness and a standardized data format was generated for all the studies.

Appraisal of study quality

The initial aim of this project was also to assess the methodological quality of the studies, using the Cochrane risk of bias tool (Risk of bias 2 - RoB 2) for randomized trials and the Newcastle-Ottawa Quality Assessment Scale (NOS) for cohort and case control studies. However, as these findings were already been reported in two recent systematic reviews and would not have influenced the final analysis, study quality appraisal was not performed for this study.

Study characteristics

Characteristics of the 24 selected studies are summarized in Supplemental Table S1. We identified 1 randomized clinical trial, 4 prospective studies and 6 retrospective studies. Main outcomes after CA were assessed at hospital discharge in 1 study and between 30 days to 1 year in the others. All included studies evaluated neurological outcome using the Cerebral Performance Category (CPC) scale; a CPC 3-5 identified an unfavorable neurological outcome in all cohorts. Data about survival at hospital discharge were reported in 8 studies. Data about rhythm at the presentation of CA were available for all the considered studies; 8 studies out of 11 enrolled patients with both shockable and non-shockable rhythms.

Study Search

('heart arrest'/exp OR 'arrest, heart' OR 'asystole' OR 'asystolia' OR 'asystoly' OR 'cardiac arrest' OR 'circulation arrest' OR 'circulatory arrest' OR 'heart arrest' OR 'heart arrest, induced' OR 'heart asystole' OR 'heart standstill' OR 'induced heart arrest') AND ('extracorporeal oxygenation'/exp OR 'ecls (extracorporeal life support)' OR 'ecls therapy' OR 'ecls treatment' OR 'ecmo (extracorporeal membrane oxygenation)' OR 'ecmo support' OR 'ecmo therapy' OR

'ecmo treatment' OR 'extra corporal membrane oxygenation' OR 'extra corporeal life support'
OR 'extra corporeal membrane oxygen support' OR 'extra corporeal membrane oxygenation'
OR 'extra corporeal membrane oxygenator support' OR 'extra corporeal membrane oxygenator
therapy' OR 'extra corporeal membranous oxygenation' OR 'extra corporeal oxygenation' OR
'extra-corporeal membrane oxygena-tion' OR 'extra-pulmonary oxygen therapy' OR 'extra-
pulmonary oxygenation' OR 'extra-pulmonic oxygenation' OR 'extracorporeal membrane
oxygenation' OR 'extracorporeal oxygenation' OR 'extracorporeal oxygenization' OR
'extracorporeal circulation membrane oxygen support' OR 'extracorporeal life support' OR
'extracorporeal membrane oxygen (therapy)' OR 'extracorporeal membrane oxygen support' OR
'extracorporeal membrane oxygen-ation' OR 'extracorporeal membrane oxygenation' OR
'extracorporeal membrane oxygenaton' OR 'extracorporeal membraneous oxygenation' OR
'extracorporeal membranes oxygenation' OR 'extracorporeal membranous oxygen support' OR
'extracorporeal membranous oxygenation' OR 'extracorporeal membranous oxygenator support'
OR 'extracorporeal membranoxygenation' OR 'extracorporeal oxygenation' OR 'extracorporeal
pump oxygenation' OR 'extrapulmonary blood oxygenation' OR 'extrapulmonary membrane
oxygenation' OR 'extrapulmonary oxygen therapy' OR 'extrapulmonary oxygenation' OR
'membrane oxygenation, extracorporeal' OR 'oxygenation, extracorporeal') AND
('resuscitation'/exp OR 'bystander cpr' OR 'cardio pulmonary resuscitation' OR
'cardiopulmonary resuscitation' OR 'chest compression' OR 'reanimation' OR 'resuscitation' OR
'resuscitation orders') AND ('mortality'/exp OR 'excess mortality' OR 'mortality' OR 'mortality
model' OR 'neurologic disease'/exp OR 'autoimmune diseases of the nervous system' OR
'nervous disease' OR 'nervous disorder' OR 'nervous system disease' OR 'nervous system
diseases' OR 'nervous system disorder' OR 'neural disease' OR 'neurogenic disease' OR
'neurologic complaint' OR 'neurologic disease' OR 'neurologic disorder' OR 'neurologic
disturbance' OR 'neurologic dysfunction' OR 'neurologic manifestations' OR 'neurologic sign'

OR 'neurologic symptom' OR 'neurologic syndrome' OR 'neurological complaint' OR
'neurological deficiency' OR 'neurological disease' OR 'neurological disorder' OR 'neurological
disturbance' OR 'neurological sign' OR 'neurological symptom' OR 'neurological syndrome' OR
'sign, neurologic' OR 'symptom, neurological')

List of requested variables

1. Name of the center
2. Matched or randomized study
3. Age
4. Male gender
5. Year of admission
6. Intensive Care Unit (ICU) Length of stay
7. Comorbidities (i.e. chronic heart failure, defined as NYHA III-IV; arterial hypertension; coronary artery disease; diabetes; chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; previous cerebrovascular disease; chronic renal failure; liver cirrhosis)
8. Arrest characteristics (i.e. location; witnessed; bystander cardiopulmonary resuscitation; cause of arrest; initial heart rhythm; time to end of resuscitation)
9. Use of ECPR
10. Lactate levels on admission
11. Use of coronary angiography
12. Use of targeted temperature management (i.e. active cooling with body temperature $<36^{\circ}\text{C}$)
13. Last day of follow-up (since arrest)
14. Survival
15. Neurological Outcome using the Cerebral Performance Category Scale at the last day of follow-up

16. Organ donation candidate; organ donation

Supplemental Figure 1. Flow-chart of the systematic review.

Supplemental Figure 2. Kaplan-Meier plot of the survival curves in the matched extracorporeal cardiopulmonary resuscitation (ECPR) group and the matched conventional cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CCPR) group, censored at 90 days after arrest, according to different subgroup analyses.

Supplemental Table S1: Research questions and PICOS (patient; intervention; control; outcomes).

Supplemental Table S2. Summary of the eligible studies comparing conventional CPR (CCPR) to extracorporeal CPR (ECPR).